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Effects of Stress on Growth, Behaviour and Physiological Activity in Fish

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the stresses that aquatic faunae specifically fish face and how these affect their production. Most animals experience stress, which triggers a variety of reactions involving all three regulating systems: neurological, endocrine, and immunological. Internal and environmental stresses expose fish to aquaculture settings, increasing their vulnerability to mortality and morbidity. The autonomic or limbic system is activated when the brain accumulates stress signals and processes them according to the severity, frequency, duration, and kind of stress. When the stressor is acute and short-term, the fish immune response is stimulatory, with an activation phase that specifically enhances innate responses. When a stressor is chronic, the immune response shows suppressive effects increasing the odds of infection. In general, species living close their environmental tolerance limits proved to be more susceptible to extra chemical stress. Toxicity usually increases by raising the temperature and lowering the food or nutrient levels. However, dealing with the stressor has an allostatic cost that may conflict with the immune response's requirements. The mechanisms underlying these immune regulatory changes are discussed in this paper, as well as the role of the main neuroendocrine mechanisms directly influencing the development of the immune response to stress on growth, behaviour, and physiological activity in aquatic animals, as well as their consequences.

Keywords

Stress, Immunity, Behaviour, Growth, Physiology

Introduction

In 1936, Canadian pathologist Selye introduced the stress hypothesis for the first time (Tan and Yip, 2018). The term "stress" has multiple different meanings. However, it is simply described as the instinctive reaction of organisms to numerous external or internal stimuli which has wide and complicated biological repercussions on the body. Stress, according to Barton (1997), is a series of biological processes that occur when an organism is confronted with a challenge outside of its typical range and attempts to re-establish homeostatic values. In general, stress is defined as any change in the environment that is severe enough to cause a biochemical and physiological response in the animal, such as a change in climate or management

(Schreck, 2000). Stress occurs when an organism's natural regulatory capacity is exceeded by an external demand (Koolhaas et al., 2011). The "general adaptation syndrome" (GAS) is a concept that describes how animals respond physically to stress (Selye, 1950). The GAS consists of hormonal cascade that triggers all the other stress responses. It is accomplished by behavioural responses or changes in different physiological and biochemical responses to readjust animals' biology for a new state of homeostasis, mostly through complicated endocrine connections (secretion of hormones from the adrenal glands). The physiological control of homeostasis has a wide range of negative effects for all biological systems, from pain to death (Etim et al., 2013).

The cells of an organism must be kept within closely defined physiological limitations as a basic prerequisite of life. Physiological, endocrine, and immunological responses in fish are induced by the continual biotic and abiotic changes that occur in farmed species. These reactions enable the reduction of cellular impacts and the preservation of the internal environment (homeostasis). The physiological equilibrium, or allostasis, is maintained by a variety of mechanisms. Autonomic, neuroendocrine, metabolic, and behavioural components all play a role in these processes. Stress is a response to stimuli that cause an imbalance in an organism's allostasis, and the stimulus that generate it are known as stressors. Physical (noise, vibration, pain, shock, temperature), psychological (exposure to a novel or uncontrolled environment), and social stresses are examples of stressors (i.e., space availability). There are additional stresses that affect the cardiovascular system and metabolic balance in the body (i.e., haemorrhage, exercise, heat exposure).

Stressors in fish husbandry include feeding, housing, culture techniques, transportation, disease, management practices, and variations in day length, as well as any stimuli that need the animal to respond in order to adjust to new conditions. The natural environment is made up of a variety of potentially unfriendly stresses that constantly affect on organisms, disrupting homeostasis and resulting in new adaptations that can be harmful or beneficial (Stott, 1981; Schmeller et al., 2018). Environmental disturbances, such as poor water quality or abrupt variations in water, can also induce stress in fish. The dynamic equilibrium is continually challenged by intrinsic and extrinsic stressors, especially in fish. High densities, non-natural habitats, and unusual "social situations," such as frequent handling (e.g., during vaccination procedures), transportation, overeating, and poor water quality (e.g., variable temperatures, waste products, chemicals environmental pollutants), can cause an allostatic overload that affects normal behaviours and physiology in susceptible individuals.

There is a significant variation in how fish respond to a stressor. The current physiological condition, environmental history, and current climatic variables all have an impact on a fish's stress reaction. In the initial emergency reaction stage, when an animal detects a threat, it produces a behavioural, autonomic, endocrine, or immunological response to preserve homeostasis. These components work together to control secondary stress response factors that modify the delivery of essential resources like energy and oxygen to important bodily locations, as well as damage hydro-mineral balance and the immune system. Exhaustion is the final stage when all the body's resources are eventually depleted, and the body is unable to maintain normal function. The long-term effects of repeated or prolonged stress exposures are maladaptive, compromising

other vital life processes (growth, development, disease resistance, behaviour, and reproduction), in part due to the high energy cost of generating the stress response (allostatic load). Physico-pathological diseases will occur as a result of aberrant biological activities, immune suppression, and the development of physico-pathological illnesses. Animals are unable to function as a result, resulting in lower production and reproductive efficiency. Understanding the effects of stresses on aquatic animals can help farmers raise animals in appropriate settings and use optimal management strategies to maximize reproductive and productive efficiency, as well as reduce production losses (Schmeller et al., 2018). Achieving these goals will result in more sustainable and long-lasting solutions for safeguarding aquatic animals from stress-inducing activities. As a result, the study's main purpose is to examine current research findings from literature reviews and original research papers, with a focus on the impact of stress on farmed aquatic animals.

The Effect of Stress on Growth and Production

Stress in aquaculture has a considerable influence on fish productivity, just as it does in other species. When fish are stressed, they usually expend more energy and nutrients battling the stressor, leaving less nutrients and less energy available for development and performance. Many studies have shown that different types of stresses have a negative impact on fish output and growth. Adrenaline and cortisol (ketones) are produced in considerable amounts under stressful situations, strengthening catabolism and weakening anabolism. On the other hand, this causes nutritional depletion and protein synthesis to be hampered, resulting in sluggish or even stationary growth. Protein conversion in the body is significantly increased in sludge water (*Limanda limanda*), but accumulation is minimized (Houlihan et al., 1994). Also, stress might inhibit development by reducing food intake, absorption, and utilization (VanWeerd and Komen, 1998). Acid stress can limit the food intake of *Salvelinus fontinalis* by 91 percent, according to Mackett et al., (1992).

Chronic stress has been found in several studies to have a limited negative effect on fish development by extending the activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-kidney axis. Chronic stress and dietary cortisol have been shown to affect feed conversion efficiency, resulting in a significant reduction in growth performance of sea bass (Leal et al., 2011). Cortisol is hypothesized to be a mediator between stress and other physiological activities in vertebrates, notably fish (Kijewska et al., 2016). Although it is now widely accepted that chronic stress affects growth and metabolism through the effects of cortisol, it is often difficult to detect stress and estimate the boundary of chronic stress with an increase in cortisol content in stress studies, because some of the stress environments are similar to the environmental variation that causes different growth under normal feeding conditions (such as temperature), and the difference between non-stressed and stressed animals is often subtle. In addition to the impacts of stress, animal growth may be influenced by individual characteristics among animals, such as the animals' intrinsic capacity to respond to stress, gender, and early life experience (Van Weerd and Komen, 1998).

According to recent aquaculture studies, high stocking density is a vital component that has a direct influence on fish survival, development, and productivity (Jia et al., 2016). Water quality, survival, growth, immunological responses, gene expression, and productivity are all affected by stocking density (Jia et al.,

2016; Yarahmadi et al., 2016). Oxidative stress is caused by high stocking densities, which stimulate the development of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Braun et al., 2010). In order to protect themselves from the harmful effects of reactive oxygen species, fish have both enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidative defence mechanisms (ROS). Antioxidative enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), and glutathione S-transferase (GST) that contribute to the body's enzymatic antioxidative defences are inhibited by high stocking density (Gao et al., 2018; Jia et al., 2016; Ni et al., 2014a). These enzymes require trace elements including selenium, iron, copper, zinc, and manganese for optimum function. If these trace components are not consumed enough in the diet, the antioxidant defence mechanisms become inefficient.

Effects of stress on behaviour

Animal behaviour is a significant expression of their functional adaptation to their surroundings. Fish behaviour is a stressor in and of itself (Cruz and Brown 2007; Earley et al. 2006). Many studies have found that behavioural adaptations occur before physiological stress. The fish dives to the bottom of the water and stays there in low-concentration ammonia stress, but as the concentration of ammonia increases, the fish slowly swims towards a higher position; in high-concentration ammonia stress, the fish are close to the surface, and migration and feeding activity are significantly reduced during ammonia stress (Shokr, 2020).

The most common pollutant in intensive fish culture is ammonia, which is produced by the decomposition of unconsumed fish food and/or faecal matter. Ammonia is a major hazard for the fish culture industry because it causes severe respiratory problems such as gasping, flaring opercula, asphyxia, and fish death (Lin and Chen, 2003). Nitrogen compounds have been discovered as important metabolic products in fish production in high-density aquaculture systems (Erol et al. 2010). Purple, crimson, or bleeding gills (inflamed), inflamed eyes, or anus are all symptoms of ammonia toxicity in fish. Fish may also clamp and seem deeper in colour, with red struck fins or bodies, and fish may pant for air at the water's surface, with shredded and jagged fins (Fernandes, 2003).

The microbiome influences the HPA axis, stress response, and behaviour particularly anxiety and locomotive activities in fish, as well as mammals (Sudo, 2019; Garcia-Reyero, 2018), which may alter eating behaviour and energy balance. Under hypoxic circumstances, both Nile tilapia and Carp have the similar response (Shokr, 2020; Ishibashi et al., 2002). Rainbow trout behavioural countermeasures appear to have a strong correlation with survival under severe hypoxia conditions; 60 percent of those who survived maintained a state of stability without showing fear, while those who died during the recovery period exhibited violent, explosive avoidance behaviours (Barreto et al. 2009). Furthermore, under stressful situations, fish move faster (Shokr, 2020), offensive behaviour and cognition in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) (Moreira et al. 2004; Barreto et al., 2009), and aggressiveness (Øverli et al. 2002, 2004a, b) are greatly reduced.

These studies suggest that fish behaviour effectively reduces stress. Fish reduce their activity in reaction to stress, which might be an adaptive response to their capacity to preserve energy and overcome stress. Fish congregating to the bottom of the water during ammonia stress may be a normal fear response; in the case of high ammonia concentrations, it slowly swims to the surface of the water, which could be due to respiratory

dysfunction caused by gill damage, or difficulty in gas exchange that causes the fish to stick together (Shokr, 2020). The notable disparities in catecholamine in rainbow trout plasma, which is 4 to 5 times greater than that of survival in dead fish plasma, while cortisol is lower in dead fish, may be attributed to the changes in their behaviour under severe hypoxic circumstances noted above. The rainbow trout's passive adaptation to hypoxic conditions may be crucial to its survival, whereas those who die may succumb to exhaustion as a result of strenuous activity that uses too much energy in the body (Barreto et al. 2009).

The impact of stress on immune function

Fish immune systems have been investigated for many years to see how stress affects them. The major effect of stress on immunity is suppression, according to animal studies. Stress has a wide range of effects on the immune system.

The influence of stress on hormonal immunity

The hormones regulated by two hormonal systems, those leading to the generation of corticosteroids (particularly cortisol) and catecholamines (such as adrenaline and noradrenaline and their precursor dopamine), are primarily responsible for the physiological regulation of homeostasis (Harvey et al., 1984).

The hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal (HPI) axis plays a significant role in the basic stress response in fish. The adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) and cortisol levels in the blood are elevated in this axis (Galhardo and Oliveira, 2009). ACTH is primarily responsible for glucocorticoid synthesis and secretion control. Cortisol is a major corticosteroid hormone that plays a key role in the stress response, according to Barton and Iwama (1991). However, an elevated blood cortisol level under chronic stress may decrease the response of the growth hormone/insulin-like growth factor-I (GH/IGF-I) axis (Link et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2013; Pujante et al., 2015). A secondary reaction to a stressful environment is the fluctuation of various metabolites in serum, including glucose, total protein concentration, and immunological response. Serum glucose levels can reflect the metabolic, nutritional, and immune status of finfish (van Raaij et al., 1996; Rafatnezhad et al., 2008; Ni et al., 2014a), while serum total protein levels can reflect the metabolic, nutritional, and immune status of finfish (Tahmasebi-Kohyani et al., 2012). Soft-shelled turtles' serum immunoglobulin and complement C3 and C4 levels can be reduced by acid stress (Zhou et al., 2000); starvation can inhibit the spontaneous haemolytic activity of *Oncorhynchus masou* and *Oncorhynchus masous kisutch* (Sakai, 1983); and hunting can reduce the serum complement C3 content of the golden-head sea bream (*Sparusaurata*), as well as reduce the spontaneous haemolytic activity of the classical and alternative pathways of complement (Sunyer et al., 1995). Low temperatures greatly diminish carp antibody responses to antigens, but high temperatures have little impact (Le Morvan et al., 1996).

Stress has an influence on hormonal immunity that is connected not only to the kind, severity, timing, and frequency of stress, but also to the animal's traits. In rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) (Yarahmadi et al., 2016), Amur sturgeon (*Acipenser schrenckii*) (Ni et al., 2016), and grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) (Lin

et al., 2018) under overcrowding conditions, immune associated enzymes such as serum lysozyme, complement, and immunoglobulin M (IgM). Increased blood cortisol levels may inhibit growth hormone/insulin-like growth factor-I (GH/IGF-I) axis transcription (IGF-Ia, IGF-Ib, and IGF-II) (de las Heras et al., 2015; Pujante et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2013; Link et al., 2010). High stocking density might impact physiological responses (HSP70 and HSP90, cytochrome P450 1A (CYP1A), and immune-related genes (interleukin 1, lysozyme, hepcidin antimicrobial peptide 1 (HAMP1), and tumour necrosis factor- (TNF-)) (Gornati et al., 2004; Jia et al., 2016; Yarahmadi et al., 2016).

The hypothalamus' paraventricular nucleus releases corticotrophin-releasing hormone (CRH), which causes the pituitary gland to secrete corticotrophin and the adrenal cortex to secrete corticosteroids in response to stress (mainly corticosterone and cortisol). The adrenal medulla secretes catecholamine hormones in response to the sympathetic nervous system's excitation (mainly including epinephrine and norepinephrine). When the body is under stress, it responds in three ways (Pickering, 1981). The major response is a shift in endocrine activity, with the primary goal of mobilizing energy. Catecholamines give energy in the short term by stimulating glycogen breakdown, whereas cortisol promotes glycogen, lipid, and protein catabolism in the long run (Gamperl et al., 1994; Mazeaud & Mazeaud, 1981). The secondary response, which is mostly metabolic adaptation (Van Weerd and Komen, 1998), is a sequence of physiological, biochemical, and immunological changes brought on by the primary reaction. When the stress response shifts from adaptation to maladaptation, the body's ability to withstand illnesses, reproductive capacity, and growth rate all suffer.

The influence of stress on cellular immunity

The impact of stress on cellular immunity varies. Shephard (1998) argues that mild physical activity and moderate environmental stress, such as cold, high temperature, and high altitude, can boost the immune response, but that it has an inhibitory impact on the immune response under physical fatigue and severe environmental stress. Furthermore, animals are at various levels of stress, which may have varying impacts on immunity. Crowding can reduce the number of peripheral blood lymphocytes of red sea bream (Rotllant et al., 1997); transport can reduce the number of blood lymphocytes in spot and inhibit the response of T and B lymphocytes to their source of division (Ellsaesser and Clem, 1986). White blood cells from trout (*Salmo trutta*) enhanced their phagocytic activity when exposed to saltwater, although non-specific cytotoxicity did not change significantly (Marc et al., 1995). These findings suggest that the mechanism behind the stress effect on cellular immunity is complicated.

The various impacts of stress on the immunological function of the body may be explained in a variety of ways. According to a new theory, acute stress boosts immunological function whereas chronic stress suppresses it. The immune system of the body responds to stress in a variety of ways, which is mostly represented in how people cope with stress. All of these stressors can create chronic stress in individuals, resulting in anorexia, changes in locomotor patterns, and increases in cortisol levels in the blood and serotonin levels in the brain. The diverse parts of the stress response, namely the activation of sympathetic nerves and

the activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, are connected to the differences in the body's perception and assessment of stress causes, as well as the unique ways of coping with stress. The immune system is affected by both systems. Long-term stress, particularly in difficult living situations, may overwhelm an individual's ability to cope with stress, resulting in insensitivity, and alterations in reaction induced by changes in the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal axis may be latent and one of the immunosuppression hypothesis' mechanisms. Individual characteristics such as gender, age, and psychological factors all influence the association between stress and immunity (Olf, 1999).

Stress can affect immune function by releasing corticosterone (or alcohol) and catecholamines (Rotllant et al., 1997). The majority of the impacts of stress on immunological function in fish are associated with variations in corticosterone levels (Maule & Schrek, 1990; Mazer and Iwama, 1993). Stress causes a rise in cortisol levels and a decrease in immune response capabilities, which are linked to the kind and duration of stress as well as other stress-related factors. The endocrine system, the immunological system, or other regulatory molecules from these two systems, as well as the neurological system, may all play a role in cortisol content alterations following chronic stress (Rotllant et al., 1997). Many neuroendocrine systems change as a result of stress, and the immunological function of the body can be altered in a variety of ways and at different degrees. High stocking density has been shown to affect transcription in growth (IGF-I, including IGF-Ia and IGF-Ib, and IGF-II) (Salas Leiton et al., 2010; de las Heras et al., 2015), physiological responses (heat shock proteins including HSP70 and HSP90, cytochrome P450 1A (CYP1A), glutathione S-transferase (GST) (Ni et al., 2014a, 2014b; Jia et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2018) and immune-related genes (interleukin 1 β , lysozyme, hepcidin antimicrobial peptide 1 (HAMP1), and tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) (Gornati et al., 2004; Jia et al., 2016; Yarahmadi et al., 2016).

Lysozyme is a crucial indicator of the immune system in fish, and it includes the destruction of Gram-positive bacterial cell walls (Arends et al., 1999). In fish, overcrowding stress can lower plasma lysozyme activity (Yin et al., 1995; Costas et al., 2013; Yarahmadi et al., 2015). Long-term overcrowding suppresses lysozyme transcription in the liver and kidney of Senegalese sole (Salas Leiton et al., 2010), in the skin of turbot (Jia et al., 2016), and in the head kidney of *O. mykiss* (Yarahmadi et al., 2016), as well as significantly reducing the expression of this gene in the skin of Chinese sturgeon (Long et al., 2019). In addition, alkaline phosphatase (Iger and Abraham, 2010) and acid phosphatase (Agrahari et al., 2007) are essential enzymes in the immune system of fish that are down-regulated due to stress (Tahmasebi-Kohyani et al., 2012). Alkaline phosphatase is a kind of lysosomal enzyme that protects the fish throughout the wound healing process, whereas acid phosphatase is a lysosomal enzyme that is required for the control of the autolysis process following cell death. GSTs, which are mostly soluble enzymes, play a significant role in detoxification and anti-oxidation produced by (ROs) (Brien et al., 2000). High stocking density of turbot inhibited GST expression, resulting in severe oxidative stress (Chan, 1995). MTs are cysteine-rich metal binding proteins that perform a number of tasks, including regulating intracellular metal concentrations and acting as antioxidants (Chan, 1995). When sea bass

(Gornati et al., 2004) and *Takifugu obscurus* (Kim et al., 2013) were bred in high densities, MT transcription in their livers and brains increased. In a high rearing density setting, however, the mRNA level of MT in young Chinese sturgeon remained normal (Jia et al., 2016). HAMP1 is an essential transcription gene that participates in the innate immune response and is implicated in the bacterial pathogen response. Overcrowding stress decreased HAMP1 expression in the epidermis of Chinese sturgeon (Long et al., 2019) and Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) in recent research (Salas-Leiton et al., 2010).

Effects of stress on endocrine

It is possible to forecast the link between physiology and behaviour. Øverli et al. (2002, 2005); Martins et al. (2006) and Pankhurst et al. (2008) discovered a correlation between glucocorticoid reactivity (or other central neuroendocrine processes) and feeding behaviour. Fish have been found to be more sensitive to stressors than many other vertebrates, and they have responded to stresses at levels that are typically considerably below those detectable by terrestrial animals (Nordgreen et al. 2007; Sneddon, 2012). The primary, secondary, and tertiary stress reactions in fish have been broadly classified (Iwama et al. 2004; Ellis et al. 2012). The fast release of stress hormones, catecholamines, and corticosteroids into the blood is the predominant reaction (the neuroendocrine response) (Mommsen et al. 1999). The brain-sympathetic-chromaffin cell (BSC) axis and the hypothalamic-pituitary-interrenal (HPI) axis are both activated in response to stresses (Figure 1). The head kidney's chromaffin cells produce catecholamines (adrenaline and noradrenaline) from sympathetic nerve terminals when the BSC axis is activated (Kalamarż-Kubiak, 2018). Despite all of these investigations, nothing is known about how fish behaviour influences physiological performance. The HPI axis is activated by the release of corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF) from the hypothalamus, which activates the anterior pituitary's corticotrophic cells to secrete adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH). The serotonergic brain system (SBS), according to (Winberg et al. 1997), is in charge of controlling the activity of the hypothalamic pituitary interrenal (HPI) axis, which results in a rise in plasma cortisol (Barreto et al. 2009). Fish were much less aggressive when given the selective serotonin re-uptake inhibitor fluoxetine (Perreault et al. 2003) or the serotonin precursor L-tryptophan (Hoglund et al. 2005; Lepage et al. 2005; Clotfelter et al. 2007). The use of a serotonin synthesis inhibitor (para-chlorophenylalanine) on the other hand enhanced aggressiveness (Adams et al. 1996). In this context, it is reasonable to expect a relationship between aggressive behaviour and physiological stress responses, and aggression can thus predict stress responsiveness. According to (Barreto et al. 2009), aggressive behaviour (attacks) in Nile tilapia is negatively correlated with baseline and/or confinement-induced physiological stress responses, while latency to start fighting is positively correlated.

Figure 1. The stimulation of BSC axis and HPI axis in response to stress in fish (Kalamarz-Kubiak, 2018).

Many studies have shown that stress may affect endocrine function at many levels, with cortisol being the final hormone produced in the stress response cascade. Although stress can generate raised cortisol levels (Forsatkar et al. 2017), exogenous cortisol administration made fish less aggressive (Øverli et al. 2002) and even led them to behave as subordinates (DiBattista et al. 2005). Crowding, for example, can significantly raise plasma cortisol levels in European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) (Santos et al. 2010), salmon (Mazer and Iwama, 1993), acid stress can raise plasma cortisol levels in rainbow trout (Brown, 1990) and Chinese turtle (Zhou et al, 2000), and hunting and captivity can raise plasma cortisol levels in green-backed flounder (Barnett and Pankhurst, 1998) and red bream (*Chelidonichthys kumu*) (Clearwater and Pankhurst, 1997). Stress indicators in fish include plasma cortisol, plasma glucose, and ventilatory frequency (VF) (Sager et al. 2000; Barton 2002; Barreto et al. 2003; Barreto and Volpato 2004, 2006b; Hawkins et al. 2004; Brown et al. 2005). Confinement has been shown to increase plasma cortisol (Volpato and Barreto 2001; Barreto and Volpato 2004; Massou et al. 2004) and VF in Nile tilapia (Barreto and Volpato 2004; Moreira and Volpato, 2004), and (Barreto et al., 2009) found elevated cortisol, glucose, and VF in Nile tilapia after confinement stress.

Other stressors, on the other hand, have been proven to increase plasma glucose (Ishibashi et al. 2002; Corrêa et al. 2003; Barreto and Volpato 2006a), therefore (Barreto et al. 2009) speculated that it was in response to a confinement stressor. The sampling procedure has a lot to do with the concentration of plasma cortisol. In contrast, while the hostility demonstrated towards an intruder in their native habitat did not differ between the high and low-responding lines of this species, the high-responding fish were more hostile when faced with the same challenge in an unfamiliar environment (Schjolden et al. 2005). These studies show how stress response influences behaviour. The plasma cortisol response of male tilapia trapped in tanks with hooks and wires is

lower than that of fish caught in nets without tanks (Foo and Lam, 1993). Furthermore, the kind of fish, stage of sexual maturation, season, temperature, and technique of getting plasma can all influence plasma cortisol concentration (Gamperl et al. 1994).

TABLE 1. Examples of mean (\pm SE) plasma cortisol concentrations in selected juvenile freshwater fishes before and 1 hr after being subjected to an identical 30-sec aerial emersion (handling stressor).*

Species	Cortisol (ng/ml)	
	Pre-stress	Post-stress
Pallid sturgeon <i>Scaphirhynchus albus</i>	2.3 \pm 0.3	3.0 \pm 0.3
Hybrid sturgeon <i>S. albus</i> x <i>platyrhynchus</i>	2.2 \pm 0.4	3.2 \pm 0.3
Paddlefish <i>Polyodon spathula</i>	2.2 \pm 0.6	11 \pm 1.8
Arctic grayling <i>Thymallus arcticus</i>	1.1 \pm 0.3	26 \pm 4.4
Rainbowtrout (domestic) <i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	1.7 \pm 0.5	43 \pm 3.5
Common carp <i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	7.4 \pm 2.9	79 \pm 14
Brook trout <i>Salvelinus fontinalis</i>	3.4 \pm 1.1	85 \pm 11
Yellow perch <i>Perca flavescens</i>	8.1 \pm 1.2	85 \pm 12
Bull trout <i>Salvelinus confluentus</i>	1.0 \pm 0.3	90 \pm 11
Brown trout <i>Salmo trutta</i>	2.8 \pm 0.4	94 \pm 11
Lake trout <i>Salvelinus namaycush</i>	11 \pm 4.4	129 \pm 11
Walleye <i>Stizostedion vitreum</i>	3.4 \pm 1.1	229 \pm 16

* All species were acclimated to their respective environmental preferenda and are listed in order of increasing magnitude of their plasma cortisol concentration 1 hr after the disturbance (from Barton and Zitzow, 1995; Barton and Dwyer, 1997; Barton et al., 1998, 2000; Barton, 2000; and unpublished data for common carp [N. Ruane, Wageningen University], yellow perch [A. H. Haukenes, University of South Dakota] and Arctic grayling [B. A. B. and W. P. Dwyer, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Bozeman Fish Technology Center]).

Stress causes a rise in plasma cortisol content that occurs later in time than adrenocorticotrophic hormone. When rainbow trout plasma is dehydrated for 5 minutes and then imprisoned for 25 minutes, adrenocorticotrophic hormone peaks just 5 minutes after stress, whereas cortisol begins to rise after 5 minutes, and plasma melanogen and adrenocorticotrophic hormone are both raised at the same time (Kim, 2018). Because cortisol production is regulated by adrenocorticotrophic hormones, cortisol has a delayed response to excitement. Although several variables influence cortisol release, the pituitary gland is the most significant. In all vertebrates, adrenocorticotrophic hormone is the cortical class that modulates pituitary control under stress and is the most essential factor in sterol secretion. Melanin can work in lieu of adrenocorticotrophic hormone depending on the sort of stress (Pandolfi et al. 2003). Corticosteroids, on the other hand, suppress the response of adrenocorticotrophic hormones and cortisol to stress (Thomas and Robertson, 1991) by negative feedback at the hypothalamus and pituitary level (Alderman et al. 2012). The fish hypothalamic-pituitary-interrenal tissue axis is fed back inhibitory by greater cortisol levels in the blood plasma on the one hand, and boosted by continually perceiving stress stimulation on the other, in the event of chronic stress (Winberg, 1997). Cortisol, for example, suppresses the rainbow trout pituitary gland's release of adrenocorticotrophic hormones when it is triggered by various adrenocorticotrophic hormone-releasing factors (Alderman et al. 2012).

Stress has an inhibitory influence on sex hormones, according to existing research. After being captured and imprisoned in farmed snapper (*Pagrus auratus*), plasma estradiol and testosterone reduced considerably (Cleary et al. 2000), which is similar with the findings of (Paolucci et al. 1990) on eating frogs (*Rana esculenta*). A similar behaviour may be seen while hunting stressed male crocodiles (Jessop et al. 2003). Stress-induced sex hormone decrease may be linked to higher cortisol levels. Through local action on the gonads or suppression of the hypothalamic-pituitary axis, cortisterone may decrease the production or release of sex hormones (Paolucci et al., 1990). Female frogs (*Litoria ewingi*) were incarcerated for 0 to 24 hours after being captured from the wild during the yolk-generating stage, and while corticosterone levels increased significantly over time, plasma estradiol and testosterone levels remained unchanged, suggesting that the yolk occurrence period regulates the amphibian response to captivity stress. Captivity has a minor influence on frog sex hormones and cortisol levels, which varies significantly depending on the stage of the sexual cycle (Paolucci et al., 1990).

Conclusion

Regardless of whether biotechnology is involved, exposing animals to unwarranted stress degrades animal welfare. Stress is crucial and should be eliminated wherever possible since it might harm such an important function as reproduction. As a fish keeper, it is extremely important to consider the effects of stress. Planning, careful control of the environment and management of the fish population are fundamental basics in fishkeeping. Less stress means less disease. In recent years, the research on stress has shifted from individual performance and traits to changes in the internal functions of tissues, organs, and cells. With the further in-depth research of cell and molecular biology, the research in this area has achieved preliminary results. Anti-stress drugs given through feed and drinking water or other ways have proven to have obvious anti-stress effects.

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